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Unraveling the Past, Shaping the Future: A Qualitative Study on Historical Development of Colleges of Education in Oyo State (1980-2020)

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Abstract

This study examined the historical development of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria, from 1980 to 2020 by revealing the evolution, enrollment of students, growth of staff and challenges of the colleges of education in Oyo State. The study employed a historical research design. Also, an interview schedule and a researchers' designed questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Historical Analysis of Colleges of Education in Oyo State Nigeria" (QHACED) with a reliability co-efficient of 0.85 were the instruments used for data collection. The population for this study comprised of 238 stakeholders of all the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria. Both the qualitative and quantitative data analysis techniques were employed in the study. It was revealed that the trends of staffing at the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria between 1980 and 2020 were fluctuating as upward and downward movements of staffing reflected. Also, challenges facing colleges of education in Oyo State were revealed which include; inconsistency and inadequate funding, vandalism of infrastructure, constant staff resignation among others. It was therefore recommended that government should ensure that a clear staffing policy for both academic and non-academic is implemented with clear criteria for recruitment of staff for different colleges in the state. The study's conclusion offer valuable insights for educators, policymakers and researchers seeking to enhance educational outcomes in Nigeria and similar contexts.

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Keywords: Historical Analysis; Teacher Education; Colleges of Education; Past; Future

Introduction

Education is the greatest instrument that man has devised for his progress and it is a dynamic tool for change. This is why successive Nigerian governments have placed much emphasis on the development of the individual as a means to national development. Education stems out to be the sure means of developing an individual's potential. The potency of education is more evident in its globalization trends which are imbued with instrumental values of nurturing productive citizens for sustainable development (Olayanju, 2012).

The fact remains that teaching and learning depend on teachers because there can be no meaningful socio-economic and political development in any country without teachers. It is teachers' numbers, quality, and devotion that test the effectiveness of all educational arrangements, development, and growth. Even the educational planners may have the best educational policies, designs, and the government may vote the largest sum of its revenue to education, but the ultimate realisation of any set of aims for education depends on the teacher. It is the teacher who will ultimately be responsible translating educational policies into action and practice. Ukeje (1996) supported this fact when he stated that education unlocks the door to modernization and it is the teachers who hold the key to that door.

According to Afe (2015), the realisation of educational objectives depends on the quality and quantity of the available teaching manpower. This can be influenced by the availability of adequate training and retraining programmes for those about to teach and those already teaching respectively. Hence, the efficiency of teacher training should be the main determining factor in the success or failure of education to meet the country's needs. The training encompasses the knowledge of the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community.

Teacher education refers to the preparation of teachers towards the attainment of attitudes, skills, and knowledge considered desirable to make them efficient and effective in their work, according to the needs of a given society at any point in time. It

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includes training and education occurring at teacher training institutions such as College of Education before the commencement of service (pre-service) and during service (in-service or on-the-job). Every society requires adequate human and material resources to improve its social organisation, preserve the culture, enhance economic development, and reform the political structures (Oke, 2019). Education is often seen as a prerequisite for quality manpower development and the creation of wealth, a sure path to success in life and service to humanity. Thus, teachers have an important role to play to adequately preparing the young for their roles in society to achieve the set national objectives.

Abdullahi (2006) stressed that education is the bedrock of the economic development of any nation. The achievement of this depends largely on the quality of the teacher education in the country. The National Policy on Education Section 8, Sub-section 70 (a) pointed out that “Teacher education programme will continue to be given a major emphasis in all our educational planning and development because no educational system can rise above the quality of its teacher” (FGN, 2013, p.33). The statement implies that teachers should be properly trained to achieve excellence. This means that the quality of teachers in the system determines the quality of the educational system of any nation in the world.

Adewuyi and Ogunwuyi (2002) opined that teacher education is the provision of professional education and specialised training within a specified period for the preparation of individuals who intend to develop and nurture young ones into responsible and productive citizens. It is informed by the fact that teaching is an all-purpose profession that stimulates the development of the mental, physical, and emotional powers of students. Such educated citizens would be sensitive and equipped with the skills and attitudes necessary for co-existence, environmental management, and a democratic process.

The heartbeat of manpower development and training for prudent use and sustenance of resources in nation-building is teacher education. Teacher education, being inextricably linked with general education and social goals, is constantly caught up in the series of dilemmas derivable from educational expansion, political, technological development, and social change. The prevailing crisis in Nigerian education and its society as typified by unemployment, poverty, corruption, crime, indiscipline, and

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underutilization of capacities in all facets of human life and national development, could be ascribed to the neglect of teacher education and the pitiable plight of the teachers. All these conflictual relationships precipitated poverty-induced hardships across all segments of the Nigerian community. What structurally becomes important in achieving the nation's quest for a self-reliant society, imbued with a vibrant economy and productive citizenry, is to put in place a comprehensive teacher education programme.

Literature Review

Oyo State is located in the South-west geo-political zone of Nigeria. it is one of the three states carved out of the former Western State of Nigeria in 1976. Oyo State consists of 33 Local Governments and 29 Local Council Development Areas. Local Government Areas are Afijio, Akinyele, Atiba, Atisbo, Egbeda, Ibadan North, Ibadan North-East, Ibadan North-West, Ibadan South-East, Ibadan South West, Ibarapa Central, Ibarapa East, Ibarapa North, Ido, Irepo, Iseyin, Itesiwaju, Iwajowa, Kajola, Lagelu, Ogbomoso North, Ogbomoso South, Ogo-Oluwa, Olorunsogo, Oluyole, Ona-Ara, Oorelope, Oriire, Oyo East, Oyo West, Saki East, Saki West and Surulere. The Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) are: Aare Latosa, Afijio West, Ajorosun, Akinyele East, Akinyele South, Akinyele West, Akorede, Araromi, Atisbo South, Ibadan East, Ibadan South East, Ibadan West, Ibarapa North-East, Ibarapa North-West, Ifelaju, Iganna, Inukan, Irepodun, Iseyin South, Iwa, Lagelu North, Ogbomoso Central, Ogbomoso South-West, Ogo-oluwa West, Oke 'badan, Omi Apata, Surulere North, Surulere South, Wewe (<https://old.oyostate.gov.ng/about-oyostate>) With a total land area of 28,454 square kilometers, Oyo State is home to nearly 5 million people, mostly Yoruba, but also other migratory communities. Ogun State borders it to the south, Kwara State borders it to the north, Ogun State and the Republic of Benin border it to the west, and Osun State borders it to the east. The terrain is composed of old hard rocks and dome-shaped hills that climb gradually from 500 meters above sea level in the south to 1,219 meters above sea level in the north. As of 2006, the population of Oyo was 5591589 million based on the Nigeria 2006 Census with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 29.8. Presently, the state is headed by a Governor, Engr. Oluwaseyi Abiodun Makinde.

Teacher Education at the early stage of the missionary period started with a few African converts who were taught how to teach and were gradually incorporated into the teaching activities in the Church after Sunday services, sometimes during the week.

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Early schools started as boarding types as missionaries opened schools in their church premises, where selected students were trained as evangelist teachers (Boyi, 2014). In 1859, the CMS showed leadership when it established a teacher training institution in Abeokuta. This was later relocated to Lagos in 1896 after the missionaries were expelled from Abeokuta due to some disagreements between the missionaries and the local population authorities most of whom were not very receptive to the new religion and the education being introduced by the missionaries. The preponderance of British presence and security assurance in Lagos influenced the decision to relocate to Lagos (Boyi, 2014).

Subsequently, the institution was moved to Oyo which became St. Andrew's College, Oyo. The Southern Baptist Mission started a Theological College at Ogbomoso in 1753. This was changed to Baptist College and incorporated teacher training courses in 1897. The College was later moved to Shaki and then to Iwo as a teachers' College. In 1905, the Wesleyan Methodist Missionary Society funded an institution for the training of Catechists and teachers in Ibadan for like a purpose to cater for students from Niger (Ukeje, 1996). It opened with four students. The number of students had risen to twenty by 1918 and the institution became known as the Wesley College, Ibadan.

In Oyo State, the first teacher training institution known as Grade II Teachers' College was established in 1896 and was later upgraded by the government of the Late Chief Bola Ige of Oyo State during the second republic in September 1980 to St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo and later Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo. In other words, Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo is an offshoot of the St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo which was upgraded to a College of Education Campus under the then Oyo State College of Education, Ila-Orangun in 1980. Thus, at various times, the College had been known as St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo, Oyo State College of Education, Oyo, and now Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo in 2008 in memory of the renowned educationist and an Andrian, Rev. Canon Emmanuel Alayande without affecting the core mandate as stipulated in the College Enabling Law. Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo was also created in the year 1977 (<https://eacoed.edu.ng/about-us>)

Following the publication of the National Policy on Education (1998), the policy articulated the dream of having a Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) as the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession. This dream was realized

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by the establishment of the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) by enabling Decree No.3 of April 1989. Furthermore, the then Military Head of State, General Abdulsalam Abubakar welcomed the need to license private investors in the provision of higher education in Nigeria, and as a result of this, more private colleges of education were established in Nigeria, particularly in Oyo State. Private investors also played their part in establishing more colleges to support the government-owned and to create room for more student enrollment.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to trace the historical development of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. Specifically, the study intends to:

- i Trace the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria before 1980
- ii Trace the trends in the area of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020
- iii Assess the trends of students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020
- iv assess the major challenges faced by the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020

Research Questions

The following questions were raised.

- 1.What were the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State?
- 2.What was the trend of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?
- 3.What were the trends of students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?
- 4.What were the major challenges the colleges of education faced in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?

Methodology

In this study, historical research method was employed. A historical research method is considered appropriate for this study because the study is purely historical.

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Historical research is a systematic method in which the researcher investigates past events to have a better understanding of the past and the present and have a reliable prediction of the future to shape it for the better (Alabi, 2021). The population of this study comprised of all the stakeholders of all the seven (7) colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria. The stakeholders are categorised into three using stratified sampling techniques. These include, the policymakers (officials of the Ministry and principal officials), implementers (Lecturers) and beneficiaries (students). Purposive sampling technique was used to select seven (7) Provosts, seven (7) Deputy Provosts Administration, seven (7) Deputy Provosts Academic, seven (7) Registrars, seven (7) Librarian, seven (7) Bursars and seven (7) Directors of works from each of the seven (7) colleges of education which is equal to forty-nine (49) principal officials. Also, 140 lecturers, seven (7) officials from the Oyo State Ministry of Tertiary Education and 42 students were selected to make a total number of 238 respondents for this study. A researchers' designed questionnaire with the reliability coefficient of 0.85, official documents and pro forma were used for data collection in this study while the data collected were analysed using the thematic analysis, the descriptive statistics of percentage and bar chart were explored to answer the research questions raised.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: *What were the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State?*

The historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria are deeply rooted in the actions and inactions of missionary bodies, colonial masters and indigenous people's movements towards formal education. In the 19th century, the missionary bodies like Wesleyan Methodist Society, Church Missionary Society (CMS), Baptist Mission and so on found their ways in Nigeria for evangelism. However, for their message to be appreciated there was need to teach people how to read and write, hence the establishment of schools. The curricula for the schools included religious education, basic reading, and writing as well as simple arithmetic. By late 19th and early 20th century, missionary schools started practicing some trends of teacher training in apprentice manner. Therefore, In the past, the training of teachers was mostly done on the job and many of them rise from student-teachers under the supervision of a more experienced teacher. Also, in 1925, the colonial government set Phelps-Stokes Commission of 1925. Among the outcomes of this commission was the call for improvement of the teacher training institution to enhance the quality of

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education available in the colony. After the Second World War, the colonial government started establishing government owned teacher training colleges in the 1930s and the 1940s. Several teacher training institutions were established during this period in Oyo State. In 1970s, Nigeria experienced a colossal expansion in her educational system and this led to the establishment of specialized institutions that offered training for teachers exclusively and also, the government of Oyo State later upgraded most of the existing teacher training institutions into full-fledge colleges of education. These colleges were meant to give higher qualifications like the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) which is a basic requirement for teaching in Nigerian schools.

Research Question 2: *What was the trend of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020?*

The trends of staffing in colleges of education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020 evolved significantly, reflecting changes in educational policies, funding and demand for specialized teaching personnel. The trend of academic and non-academic staffing of colleges of education in Oyo State was summarized in the Table 1:

Table 1: Trend of Academic and Non-academic Staffing in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State: 1980-2020

Years	Staff Recruitment		Total	% Increment
	Academic	Non-Academic		
1980-1982	58	61	119	-
1983-1985	101	92	193	62.18
1986-1988	120	124	244	26.42
1989-1991	215	249	464	90.16
1992-1994	302	321	623	34.27
1995-1997	411	432	843	35.31
1998-2001	512	560	1,072	27.16
2002-2004	562	591	1,153	7.56
2005-2007	601	710	1,311	13.70
2008-2011	819	1,190	2,009	53.24
2012-2014	839	1, 218	2,057	2.39
2015-2017	860	1,347	2,207	7.29
2018-2021	894	1,322	2,216	0.41

Source: Field work (2024)

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing Trends of Academic and Non-academic Staff in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020

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The table and the chart above indicate that a total of 199 staff members were in the colleges between 1980 and 1982. However, there was a massive increase of 62.18% between the year 1983 and 1985. Between 1986 and 1988, the colleges staffing trend was downward with 26.42% increment compared to previous years of 62.18%. However, the staffing trend witnessed its biggest increment till date in the years 1989-1991 with 90.16% total increments compared to previous years. This is largely due to creation of more teacher training schools in Oyo State. By 1992 to 1994, there is only 34.27% increment, which indicate downward trend compared to the previous years' massive increment. Also, 1995-1997 saw almost identical increment in the trend of staffing compared to previous years with 35.31% increment.

The transition of the Nigeria government from military to democracy did not affect peoples' interest in academic with the trend in staffing still relatively unchanged between 1998 and 2001 with 27.16% increment compared to previous years. However, there was a massive decline in the trends of colleges of education in Oyo State staffing in 2002 to 2004. This might be due to more emphasis being place on University Education which affected enrolment of students and subsequently affect employment of staff. 2002-2004 only witnessed 7.56% increment, 2005-2007 with 13.70 increment witnessed, however, there was a sharp increase in 2008-2011 with 53.24% increment. The increment experienced in 2008-2011 was as a result of establishment of more private colleges of education.

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More so, since 2012, the colleges of education staffing trends have been minimal increment with only 2.39% increment between 2012 and 2014, 7.29% increment between 2015 and 2017, 0.41% increment between 2018 and 2021 while the most recent staffing figures between 2022 and 2024 is 2,339 which is only 5.55% increment compared to previous years. In conclusion, there have been inconsistent in the trends of staff recruitment among colleges of education in Oyo State.

Research Question 3: *What were the trends of students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?*

Between 1980 and 2020, the trends of students' enrolment in colleges of education across the nation reflect educational and socio-economic growth of the nation. In Oyo State and across the country, prior to the establishment of Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), Institutions which include University, Polytechnic and Colleges of Education have a specified and standardized way of conducting their own internal admission examination and enroll students who meet their requirements. However, the policies to standardized and harmonized the education system of the country have led to JAMB conducting standardized examinations with colleges of education having a specified cut of marks for students.

Also, apart from internally conducted examinations by the colleges of education, there are other requirements that candidates must have before being consider for admission. Among them are (a) completion of secondary school education with a minimum of number of credits in relevant subjects, most especially, English and Mathematics. Table 2 below reveals students' enrolment trends in Colleges of Education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020.

Table 2: Trends of Students' Enrolment in Colleges of Education in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Academic Session	Numbers of Students		Students Enrolment within 3 Years	Percentage Increment Previous Years	% Over
	Male	Female			
1980-1982	498	109	607	-	
1983-1985	604	206	810	33.44	
1986-1988	891	451	1,342	65.68	

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1989-1991	1,412	844	2,256	68.11
1992-1994	1,738	1,008	2,746	21.72
1995-1997	2,451	1,612	4,063	47.96
1998-2001	5,682	3,810	9,492	133.62
2002-2004	6,198	4,322	10,520	10.83
2005-2007	7,856	5,041	12,897	22.59
2008-2011	8,221	5,518	13,739	6.53
2012-2014	8,044	5,001	13,045	-5.05
2015-2017	7,921	4,981	12,902	-1.09
2018-2021	7,341	6,012	13,353	3.49

Source: Field work (2024)

Figure 2: Bar Chart Showing Trends of Student’s Enrolment in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020

Table 3 shows the pattern of students’ enrolment within 3years interval. The students’ enrolment was 607 between 1980 and 1982, while there was 33.44% increment in the years 1983 to 1985. Years 1986-1988 and 1989-1991 saw massive upward increment in the numbers of students’ enrolment with 65.68% and 68.11% increment within the six years’ interval. The massive increment within these years might be as a result of appreciation of academic by the populace and the massive opportunities attached to teacher trainings. Within the year 1992 and 1994, the students’ enrolment trend falls compared to previous six years with only 21.72 increment while 1995 and 1997, the enrolment of 4,063 students shows 47.96% increment to previous years. Between 1998

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and 2001, colleges of education in Oyo State experienced massive increment in the number of students' enrolment. 133.62% increment coincided with President Obasanjo's policy of free primary education and establishment of more colleges of education. Between 2002 and 2004, the trend experienced another massive fall in students' enrolment compared to previous years. The waves of enrolment experienced between 1998 and 2001 reduced a little which affect staff recruitment across colleges of education. Only, 10.83% increment was experienced between the year 2002 and 2004.

The establishment of new colleges of education between 2003 and 2005 spark another wave of enrolment trend experienced between 2005 and 2007 with 12,897 new enrolments', making 22.59% increment compared to previous years. However, the waves came down back between 2008 and 2011 with only 6.53 increment in the number of new enrolments compare to previous years (2005-2007). Between 2012-2014 and 2015-2017, the students' enrolment experienced a massive negative trend, where there was -5.05% in number of enrolments between 2012 and 2014 and -1.09% between 2015 and 2017. According to the study finding, this is largely due to the fact, students are now more interested in University Education, Entrepreneur and other activities that they believe will fetch them more money. The negative experienced during this six year highlighted the challenges of unemployment among NCE graduates and also, poor remuneration being paid to employed NCE graduates. Between 2018 and 2021, there was slight increment compared to negative trend experienced in the previous six years, with 13,353 new enrolments which was 3.49% increment compared to previous three years (2015-2017). The trend highlighted above a high level of inconsistency in students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State especially between 1980 and 2020.

Research Question 4: *What were the major challenges the colleges of education faced in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?*

The respondents' responses to the interview highlighted that major challenges faced by colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020 were diverse and impacted the quality of education and development of the institutions. Most of these challenges include;

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1. Poor Interest of Local Communities from Onset: 72% of the respondents made mention that one major challenge was the initial lack of interest from local communities in Oyo State. Many communities viewed universities as more prestigious, leading to low enrolment and limited local support for the colleges of education. This hindered the institutions' growth and development during the early years."

2. Poor Emphasis Placed on Colleges of Education by Government Compared to Universities: Also, 63% of the respondents believe that colleges of education in Oyo State faced neglect, as the government prioritized Universities. The lower importance given to teacher training colleges affected their funding, development, and overall visibility, making it difficult for them to compete or thrive on the same level."

3. Inconsistent and Inadequate Funding: 79% of the respondents pointed out that inconsistent and inadequate funding was a persistent issue. Colleges of education in Oyo State often struggled to maintain basic infrastructure, hire qualified staff, and improve educational resources. This financial instability limited their capacity to offer quality education."

4. Poor Remuneration of Graduate Teachers by Employers: 61% of the respondents believe that graduate teachers from these colleges poor remuneration upon employment is another challenge that continues to affect enrolment and quality. Many found the pay inadequate for their qualifications, leading to dissatisfaction, demotivation, and an overall decline in the prestige of teaching as a profession."

5. Religious Crises in Local Communities: 29% of the respondents also pointed out that at some point, religious crises also posed significant challenges, particularly in communities where tensions flared. These conflicts affected the smooth operation of the colleges, disrupting academic activities and affecting student enrolment and staff retention.

6. Vandalism of Infrastructure: Vandalism of infrastructure is another important challenge pointed out by 43% of the respondent. They said that colleges suffered from the destruction of educational facilities, which led to a decline in the quality of education provided. This further discouraged investment in the sector, worsening the already fragile situation.

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7. Constant Staff Resignation Due to Poor Pay: Finally, 80% of the provosts asserted that constant staff resignation, driven by poor pay, created instability in the colleges of education. Many skilled educators sought better opportunities elsewhere, leaving the institutions understaffed and affecting the quality of education and administrative efficiency.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that the trend of staffing at the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria between 1980 and 2020 were fluctuating as upward and downward movements of staffing reflected. This was due to a lot of reasons such as strategic interventions towards improving the quality of education as well as addressing the shortage of qualified teachers in the Nigerian society. This is related to a study of Fagbemiye (2001) which submitted that several challenges characterized Nigeria post-independence educational system, one of which was the concern for the quality teachers who could provide quality education for the growing school system. The Nigerian government, realizing this need provided a high priority for the setting up of teacher training centres like colleges of education. These institutions were expected to churn out well qualified teachers to teach the post primary and secondary education. Also, in the same period the government tried to enhance the quality of education by providing teachers with important pedagogical competencies enabling them to meet the challenges of a rapidly changing educational environment (Okebukola, 2002).

Another factor that affected staffing was the increase in demand of specialized teachers. This was due to the complexity of education system in Nigeria therefore teachers with techniques in specialized areas like science, technology, and vocational education were needed. But insufficient funding and unsystematic policies on recruitment generates disparities in staffing practices which are actual thorns in this situation in many colleges of education (Ajayi, 2017).

More so, this study findings show that there are fluctuations on the student enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from the year 1980 to 2020. The reason behind this inconsistency was a change in the general economic situation, changes in government policies regarding education and the development of new forms of higher education institutions. This is in line with the finding of the study of Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2008) which asserted that in the past, some families could not be able to afford to pay the fees required to take their children to colleges of education hence low

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intakes. On the other hand, when there was improved economic development, there was an improvement in enrolments since families were better of economically to pay for their children's education.

Recommendations

1. Important policy measures such as scholarships, career advancement schemes and professional development for intending teachers should be formulated. This will encourage enrollment into teacher education programmes.
2. The government should also ensure that a clear staffing policy for both academic and non-academic is implemented with clear criteria for recruitment of staff for different colleges.
3. More so, there should be provision of enough funds to support the development of physical infrastructure and policies to be implemented by different colleges as part of physical infrastructure policies.

Conclusion

This historical analysis of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria (1980-2020) has unraveled the complex dynamics that shaped the development of teacher education in the state. The study revealed the significant role of government policies on enrolment rate, staffing, capacity building as well as challenges facing colleges of education in the state. As Nigeria continues to navigate the complexities of 21st-century education, this study highlights the importance of understanding the historical context of teacher education. By unraveling the past and shaping the future, colleges of education in Oyo State can continue to play a vital role in producing qualified educators and driving educational excellence.

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